

The Transformation of Design Imagery of Gorga in Toba Batak Houses

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Abstract. For the Batak Toba in the North Sumatera, Indonesia, ornamental woodcarvings in the walls of the traditional Batak Toba house known as ‘*gorga*’ are used as a symbol to show the status of the homeowners as well as the magical protection for the inhabitants of the house. Each motif of the *gorga* has a symbolic meaning based on the belief system of the Batak Toba. The making of *gorga* before the house construction must follow certain rules that have been mutually agreed upon in traditional customs of Batak Toba society and should not be violated. In the development, the *gorga* undergo design transformation and meaning with the addition of values from outside the traditional Batak Toba community system. This paper focuses on developing an understanding of the logic of the design transformation in the *gorga*. The analysis was done using visual analysis method with the interpretive-historical research with certain design strategies

1. Introduction

Gorga is an ornamental carving on the outer walls and sometimes also on the inner walls of the traditional Batak Toba houses. Traditionally the skill of engraving the ornamental *gorga* is passed down orally from one of the experts to their descendants or apprentices. Geometrically the ornamental *gorga* supposedly take inspiration from the various geometric shapes of plants, humans, natural objects, celestial objects and animals.

According to Panggabean (1997) *gorga* is a marker of a house considered as a sacred dwelling. It contains symbolic meaning based on the belief system in Batak Toba society. Waterson (1998: 120) and Niessen (1985: 210) note that the ornaments of *gorga* engraved in Batak Toba houses have a symbolic meaning of divine power to protect the inhabitants. In the absence of *gorga*, the house construction process is considered imperfect. The engraving of *gorga* must follow the strict rules such as the lines should not be broken. If the *gorga* engraving flow line is cut off, it is believed that it will bring bad luck and havoc to the inhabitants of the house.

Gorga has an important role in the architectural practice in Batak Toba society. As noted by Anggeler (2016: 311) in the legend of world creation based on Batak Toba belief, *Nang Gorga di Portibi*. In the legend, the goddess *Nang Gorga di Portibi* was the daughter of Batara Guru and creator of the earth, who was known as *Boru Deak* or *Dayang Parujar*. The word *gorga* in her name denoted wood-carving but it was also meaning ‘Woman who is a skilled speaker in the world’. This means the house with *gorga* carving is the house protected with goddess words.

According to another legend recorded by Simanjuntak (2012: 147), after *Si Boru Dayang Parujar* forged the earth with words and conquer the devil, *Naga Padoha*, She asked his father to send her fiancée down from heaven to earth. The name of her fiancée was called *Si Tuan Ruma Uhir Si Tuan Ruma Gorga* which means the owner of the carved house.

In the development, the *gorga* design underwent physical transformation and symbolic meaning with the addition of values from outside the traditional Batak Toba community system. According to Azmi (2004) and Sitindjak (2011) there were some modifications and deformation of appearance and symbolic values in *gorga* carving on some of the new vernacular houses and other buildings around Samosir Island.

2. Research Method

The methodology of this research is based on an analytical review on visual comparability and interpretive-historical research. The visual comparability will be analyze with data from visual documentation that is collected from several field visits by recording a variety of *gorga* found in several vernacular houses and buildings. The visual documentation then converted into visual matrix using Computer Aided Design software. The interpretive-historical research was based on investigation system of interpretation, using data or empirical evidence from archives, documents, data from the field visits and interviews with the house owners.

3. Theoretical Perspective

The visual linguistic properties of architecture have long been noted in a generalized metaphorical way. It can be applied also to the decoration of a house. Each shape in decoration or any insignia on the wall or structure of a house can be seen as an occasion for the development or evolution of some new vocabulary of forms. Tipple (1992) described transformation as a form of change, which was commonly termed incremental, development, subtraction, or attrition (reduction in size) and total alteration or rebuilding. It is synonyms with the term of evolution.

Each development of the shape of house decoration sometimes also applied a new meaning to the symbol. The definition of symbolism according to Merriam-Webster is “The art or practice of using symbol especially by investing things with a symbolic meaning or by expressing the invisible or intangible by means of visible or sensuous representations: as artistic imitation or invention that is a method of revealing or suggesting immaterial, ideal or otherwise intangible truth or states.

According to Waterson (1998: 17), the architecture was not only about the existence of shelter against the weather but also the involvement of social and symbolic space which reflected the values of its creator and occupants. It is also applied to the decoration or insignia of the house.

Leeuwen (2014: 94) described the key idea of house decoration as visual symbol is the layering of meaning. The first layer is denotation which describe of ‘what or who is depicted of the symbol?’ (literal or the obvious meaning of a symbol) and the second layer is connotation of ‘what ideas and values are expressed through what is represented and through the way in which it is represented?’ (Socio-cultural and personal associations of a symbol). The denotation and connotation of a visual symbol change from time to time with the addition of new elements in the society, like religion, technology, etc.

3.1. *Jabu: The House*

According to Panggabean (1997: 14) Toba Batak vernacular building based its form basically has two types, *Jabu* and *Sopo*. *Jabu* (house) are divided into three types; *Jabu Batara Guru* or *Ruma Gorga* (house with *gorga*), *Jabu Batara Siang* (house without *gorga*) and *Jabu Sibaba Ni Amporik* (small house or peasant house). *Sopo* (granary) are divided into two types; *Sopo Godang* (large rice granaries which also serves as a meeting place) and *Sopo Eme* (small rice granaries).

The anatomy of *Jabu Batara guru* or *Ruma Gorga* are divided into three parts; *Banua Toru* (substructure), *Banua Tonga* (the body of the house where people lives) and *Banua Ginjang*

(superstructure). The *gorga* only applied into *Banua Tonga* and *Banua Ginjang* because *Banua Toru* is considered unholly where the spirit and the animals live (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Anatomy of *Jabu Batara Guru* or *Ruma Gorga*.

3.2. The Gorga

Although *gorga* can be considered pictograms or ideograms, the pictorial messages in *gorga* are not always as obvious as in other culture glyphs. The shapes are not designed to be read phonetically like letters or words as in the case of Chinese characters or hieroglyphs like in ancient Egypt. In *gorga* designs, subject and meanings can be expressed as two types: abstract patterns, where the actual subject is not directly recognizable, or figurative patterns, which directly depict their subject shape. *Gorga* wood carving which applied in the *Jabu* can be divided into several types based on the shape design of the motif and the colors. Based on the color, *gorga* are separated into two types. *Gorga silingggom* is dominated by black and *gorga sipalang* is dominated by red. White color is used on both *gorga*. Based on the pattern design, originally the *gorga* are divided into five types (see figure 2).

3.2.1. Animals Pattern

Gorga that take the form of various types of animals, both common animal encountered on daily life like horses, buffalo, lizard as well as the mythical animals like naga (snake). As example, in figure 2 we can see pattern A1 is *hoda-hoda* which depicts horses shape and pattern B1 is *boraspati* which depicts the sacred lizard

3.2.2. Anthropomorphic Pattern

Gorga that take the form of human or parts of the human bodies including supernatural human beings such as giants or gods. As example, in figure 2 pattern A2 is *adep-adep* which depicts female breast and pattern B2 is *gorga jorngom* which depicts giant creature's face.

3.2.3. Astronomical Pattern

Gorga that take the form of various types of astronomical objects that can be observed by human eyes. These motifs design may consist of single or combined of various objects. As example, in figure

2 pattern A3 is *mataniari* which depicts as the sacred sun, the life giver and pattern B3 is *desa na ualu* which depicts eight cardinal point.

3.2.4. Geometric Pattern

Gorga with repeatable patterns design obtained by using simple mathematical measurement. The basic shapes are parallel lines, circles, triangles, rectangles and others. As example, in figure 2 pattern A4 is called *sitompi* and pattern B4 is called *iran-iran*.

3.2.5. Vegetative Pattern

Gorga that take the shape of various vegetative types objects like plants and trees or parts of it. Usually it is geometrically shaped and to accompaniment other patterns that are arranged in a continuous method. As example, in figure 2 pattern A5 is called *simeol-eol masioloan* and pattern B5 is called *silintong*. Both are depicts as water based vegetation.

Figure 2. *Gorga*'s pattern design types

4. Visual Analytical Findings

Visual analysis is used for comparisons of the development of the *gorga*'s engraving forms design. Some finding is compared with archives documents to determine the origin of the pattern design.

4.1. *Gorga Desa Na Ualu and Gorga Bindu Matoga*

Gorga Desa Na Ualu pattern is a *gorga* that depict eight cardinals. This *gorga* is made as a symbol of seasonal astrology. This pattern is a simplification from *bindu matoga* which shows the concentric conception of space consisting of two squares turned over forty-five degrees.

According to Watterson (1998: 95) the Toba Batak, whose language includes a significant proportion of Sanskrit derived words including *desa* for 'cardinal points' and *bindu* for 'centre point'. Thus *desa na ualu* means 'eight cardinal points' and *bindu matoga mean* 'powerful power-point'. These eight-pointed design very likely are derived from Indian mandalas.

Desa na ualu and *bindu matoga* sometimes circled by the *naga* or snake which correlate to pre-Hindu ideas where the *naga* controlled the four compass points (*Nagamandala* depicted at Padmanabhaswarny temple in India from 300 AD – see figure 3).

Desa na ualu and *bindu matoga* patterns are mainly found at the top of the house entrance area called *dorpi jolo*. In its development these two *gorgas* undergoes a shape change from rectangle to rounder shape and from a serpent-like form into a floral shape. This was discovered by the author at the time of data collecting survey in Simanindo village on Samosir Island (see figure 4).

Figure 3. The evolution of *gorga desa na ualu* and *gorga bindu matoga* compared with Hindu's *nagamandala*.

Figure 4. The transformation of *gorga desa na ualu* design pattern from rectangular to rounder shape.

4.2. *Gorga Jorngom*

Gorga Jorngom is an anthropomorphic pattern shaped like a giant creature. It is placed in *haling godang* which is located above the entrance. It is symbolized the protector of the house with the power of rejecting all kinds of crimes and sicknesses. According to Panggabean (1998: 28) *Jorngom* is the evolution form of the Hindu's *kalamakara*.

Figure 5. The evolution of *gorga jorngom* from *kalamakara*; *kalamakara* (left) – *gorga jorngom* (above-middle) – new interpretation of *gorga jorngom* (right).

The *kalamakara* which located at the apex of the lintel arch of entrance door in Hindu architecture consists of a combination of *makara* and *kala-mukha* (Dumarcaay 2002:42). According to Snodgrass (1992) the *kalamakara* symbolized destruction and creation, death and life, darkness and solar light. In Buddhist and Hindu teaching, kala opening its mouth as an entrance is represent of devouring the time. Waterson (1998: 131) mentions that in Toba Batak house, the doorways are called *baba* or ‘animal mouth’.

The *kalamakara* and original *gorga jorngom* pattern can be recognized its feature with the anthropomorphic of giant face. Some of new interpretation of *gorga jorngom* carved on the wall of new Toba Batak houses in Simanindo village has erased the face feature and changed into more curvative plant ornaments (see figure 5).

4.3. *Gorga Ulu Horbo (Ulu Paung)*

Gorga ulu horbo is a decorative *gorga* that is placed at the gable of the roof in the form of a giant horned face. According to Waterson (1998: 131) *ulu horbo* was evolutes from buffalo head because Toba batak’s house was a representation of a buffalo’s body. Domenig (2014: 395) noted that gable horns based on the buffalo head and ornamented with vegetal motifs could be seen in many regions of Indonesia including Toba Batak houses. Korn (1953: 101) documented one of the ritual poems of Toba Batak asking good fortune with the expression of a buffalo horn as a decoration on the ridge beam of the house.

Tanduk ni horbo paung
Sangkot di bungkulan ni ruma
Mamora anak bao
Gabe nampuna huta

Translated as

The horns of the festive buffalo
 Hang on the ridge beam of the house
 Rich be the *boru* clan
 Blessed be the owner of the village

According to Winkler (1925: 22) The buffalo horns on Toba Batak house roof were actually taken from an animal that was sacrificed at the inauguration of the house and their function was ‘to continuously remind the ancestors that they are obliged by the sacrifice to protect and bless their descendants living in the house’.

Gorga ulu horbo is also commonly depicted holding up a bowl in its head. In Toba Batak culture there is a house cleansing ceremonial dance called *sawan* dance (*sawan* can be translated as a bowl) where a female shaman dancing in front of the house with a bowl containing the offerings to the ancestors.

Figure 6. The evolution of *ulu horbo* from buffalo head; Buffalo head with real horns on Toba Batak house circa 1935, courtesy of KITLV (left) – common *gorga ulu horbo* (middle) – new interpretation of *ulu horbo* (right).

From figure 6 we can see the changing form of *ulu horbo* from actual buffalo head with real horns into anthropomorphic of giant's face with horns. The wooden *gorga* face horns further are adorned with carving that represented plant motif. However in the further development, the plant motif became more dominating as found on several new houses in Simanindo village, Samosir Island.

4.4. *Gorga Mataniari*

Gorga mataniari takes the shape of the sun and is manifested geometrically in the form of a closed curve that forms four spheres on the left, right, top and bottom of a square. It is symbolize the life strength and source of life where the course of human life itself parallels with the passage of the sun from east to the west (Waterson 1998: 94). It is a possibility that *gorga mataniari* also have an Indian culture background. One of the hypothesis is it is depiction of *Sudarshana Chakra*. *Sudarshana Chakra* is a spinning, disk-like weapon which belongs to Hindu god Vishnu. There is another shape of *gorga mataniari* that took a circular shape with four cardinals and sometimes paired with *gorga dalihan no tolu* depicted as three-pronged motifs which under Hindu influence represent another weapon belongs to Shiva, the trident (Waterson 1998: 95). Shiva according to Hindu ideas controls the compass points where the sun rises from the east and sets to the west. *Gorga mataniari* can be found on the left and right side of front wall supporting beam named *dorpi jolo* which is positioned above the entrance.

Figure 7. Different types of *gorga mataniari*; (a) rectangular *mataniari* – the most common shape; (b) circular *mataniari* and (c) *dalihan no tolu*.

The merging of the *mataniari* and *dalihan no tolu* evolves into a new shape which usually depicted on the gable supporting beam of the house. There is one odd motif which took the shape of sunflower's *mataniari* that was found on a new built house at Simanindo village.

Figure 8. The merging types of *gorga mataniari* and *dalihan no tolu*; (d) with four cardinals; (e) with three cardinals; (f) sunflower shape, found in one of the new Toba Batak house at Simanindo village.

5. Conclusions

Based on visual analysis that has been done on four motifs found in several Samosir island's vernacular Toba Batak houses we found *gorga* woodcarving has undergone several changes in shape and meaning. More complex motifs in older houses are usually simplified when building a new home. Based on the interpretive historical approach we also found at least four *gorga* motifs were influenced by Hindu-Indo culture at first before they undergo evolution of form and meaning.

In the past *gorga* regarded as inherently powerful and may serve as protective function for the occupants. Without the addition of the *gorga*, the construction process may not be able to complete. However in some new construction this custom is usually neglected. The *gorga* is still in use on some of the houses but it is merely served only for decoration purpose. Therefore some of the new houses are adorned with odd and simplified shape of *gorga* motifs but without actual meaning.

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References

- [1] Angerler, Johann 2016 Images of God in Toba Batak Storytelling, *Jurnal Wacana* 17 pp 303-335.
- [2] Azmi, Drs 2004 Keunikan Rumah Batak Toba: Seni Gorga Tradisi Folklor dan Arsitektur, *Jurnal Seni Rupa FBS Unimed* 1 (Juni) pp 37-51.
- [3] Bartlett, Harley H 1934 *The Sacred Edifices of the Batak of Sumatra* (Michigan: University of Michigan Press)
- [4] Domenig, Gaudenz 2014 *Religion and Architecture in Premodern Indonesia: Studies in Spatial Anthropology* (Leiden: Bijdragen tot de Tall, Land-en Volkenkunde 294 Brill).
- [5] Dumarcay, Jacques 2003 *Architecture and Its Models in South-East Asia* (Bangkok: Orchid Press).
- [6] Korn, V.E 1953 *Batakse Offeranden* (Leiden: Bijdragen tot de Tall, Land-en Volkenkunde 109 Brill).
- [7] Leeuwen, Theo van and Carrey Jewitt (ed) 2004 *Handbook of Visual Analysis* (London: SAGE Publications Ltd)
- [8] Niessen, Sandra 1985 *Motifs of Life in Toba Batak: Text and Textiles* (Dordrecht: Foris Press).
- [9] Panggabean, Drs. Herlan (ed) 1997 *Ornamen Ragam Hias Rumah Adat Batak Toba* (Medan: Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Sumatera Utara).
- [10] Sianipar, K; Gunardi G; Widyonugrahanto and Rustiyanti S 2015 Makna Seni Ukiran Gorga Pada Rumah Adat Batak, *Jurnal Panggung* 25 (3) pp 227-235.
- [11] Sitindjak, Ronald H.I. 2011 Studi Ikonologi Panofsky Pada Arsitektur dan Interior Gereja Katolik Inkulturatif Pangururan, *Jurnal Dimensi Interior* 9 (2) pp 119-136.
- [12] Snodgrass, Adrian 1992 *The Symbolism of the Stupa* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers).
- [13] Waterson, Roxana 1998 *The Living House: An Anthropology of Architecture in South East Asia* (New York: Whitney Library of Design Press)
- [14] Winkler, Johannes 1925 *Die Toba-Batak auf Sumatra in Gesunden und Kranken Tangen: Ein Beitrag zur Kenntnis des Animistischen Heidentums* (Stuttgart: Belsler).